

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Baimi Tao****FIRST NAME: VAIZI****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the purpose of academic essays?
- To entertain readers.
 - To communicate ideas based on evidence.¹**
 - To persuade readers to agree with the author's opinion.
 - To promote personal experiences.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7.

2. Why is it important to cite your sources?
- To get good grades.
 - To give credit to others.²**
 - To earn money and promotions.
 - All the above.
3. How should the title be written?
- In sentence case.
 - In all lowercase letters.
 - In all uppercase letters.³**
 - In title case.
4. Which of the following is true about the abstracts in Dissertation Abstracts International?
- They are longer than 350 words.
 - They help researchers understand the relevance of the work.⁴**
 - They are only included in American dissertations.

² Turabian L. Kate, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139-140.

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Four edition. Columbia University: SAGE, 2019), 65.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 68.

- Less than 5% of American dissertations are included in Dissertation Abstracts International.
5. The theoretical or conceptual framework of a study:
- Guides the research and analysis of findings.**⁵
 - Provides a summary of the literature review.
 - Critically analyzes previous research studies.
 - None of the above.
6. A graphic depiction of the theoretical or conceptual framework:
- Illustrates the relationships between concepts, ideas, or variables.**⁶
 - Serves as the introduction to the literature review.
 - Analyzes the gaps and debates in the literature.
 - None of the above.
7. Which of the following programs is NOT mentioned as a citation management tool?
- EndNote.
 - RefWorks.
 - Zotero.
-

⁵ Ibid., 77.

⁶ Ibid., 268.

MLA Style.⁷

8. Which chapters of the manual provide examples of notes-style citations?

Chapters 16 and 17.⁸

Chapters 18 and 19.

Chapters 20 and 21.

Chapters 22 and 23.

9. Which chapters of the manual provide examples of author-date style citations?

Chapters 16 and 17.

Chapters 18 and 19.⁹

Chapters 20 and 21.

Chapters 22 and 23.

10. What is the purpose of the WHO style guide?

To provide rules for print and electronic publications only.

To outline WHO house style for use in all information products.¹⁰

To provide guidance on publishing policies and procedures.

⁷ Turabian L. Kate, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 145.

⁸ Ibid., 9.

⁹ Ibid., 10.

¹⁰ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*. Second edition (WHO, 2013), 1-2.

- To maximize its usefulness to everyone involved in preparing WHO information products.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D. and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Columbia University: SAGE, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.